

Kinetics and mechanism of the oxidation of ethyl glycol, D-mannitol and D-sorbitol by hexacyanoferrate(III) ion in aqueous alkaline medium

H. S. Singh^{a*}, G. R. Verma^b, Arti Gupta^a and Anjali Mittal^a

^aChemical Laboratories, University of Allahabad, Allahabad-211 002, India

^bS. D. (P. G.) College, Muzzafarnagar-251 001, India

Manuscript received 3 June 1997, revised 22 April 1999, accepted 17 May 1999

The rate of oxidation of ethyl glycol, D-mannitol and D-sorbitol by hexacyanoferrate(III) ion in aqueous alkaline medium is directly proportional to the organic substrate and hydroxide ion concentrations. The dependence of rate on hexacyanoferrate(III) ion is nearly first order at lower concentrations and tends towards zero order at higher concentrations. A probable reaction mechanism has been suggested.

The kinetics of oxidation of polyhydroxy alcohols have been less studied in alkaline medium. A limited account of data dealing with alkaline permanganate¹ oxidation of diols is available¹. The kinetic data suggest that the oxidation involves the formation of a complex between the amount of substrate and $[\text{KFe}(\text{CN})_6]^{2-}$. The complex disproportionates into the free radical and $[\text{KFe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}$ ion². For further information concerning the oxidation kinetics of polyhydroxy alcohols in a aqueous alkaline medium, we report herein the results on the kinetics of oxidation of ethyl glycol, D-mannitol and D-sorbitol with hexacyanoferrate(III) ion in aqueous alkaline medium.

Results and Discussion

The kinetics of oxidation of ethyl glycol, D-mannitol and D-sorbitol were carried out in aqueous alkaline medium at constant ionic strength of the medium and temperature.

The reaction follows nearly first order kinetics at lower concentrations of hexacyanoferrate(III) ion tending towards zero order at its higher concentrations (Fig. 1). The concentration of hexacyanoferrate(III) varied for ethyl glycol, D-mannitol and D-sorbitol was 2.0×10^{-3} to 10.0×10^{-3} M, 1.0×10^{-3} to 8.0×10^{-3} M and 1.0×10^{-3} to 10.0×10^{-3} M respectively. The initial reaction rate values were calculated by plotting remaining ferricyanide ion concentration versus time.

The results presented in Figs. 2 and 3 confirm the first order kinetics with respect to substrate as well as hydroxide ion concentration respectively. The substrate concentration was 0.5×10^{-2} to 9.0×10^{-2} M for ethyl glycol, similarly 1.0×10^{-2} to 20.0×10^{-2} M for mannitol and 1.0×10^{-2} to 15.0×10^{-2} M for sorbitol. The hydroxide ion concentration was varied from 0.25×10^{-1} to 7.0×10^{-1} M for ethyl glycol, 0.5×10^{-1} to 8.0×10^{-1} M for mannitol and

Fig. 1 Effect of $[\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]$ on the reaction rate (A) [mannitol] = 8.0×10^{-2} M, $[\text{NaOH}] = 0.6$ M, $\mu = 0.8$ M at 30° , (B) [sorbitol] = 8.0×10^{-2} M, $[\text{NaOH}] = 0.5$ M, $\mu = 0.8$ M at 30° and (C) [ethyl glycol] = 5.0×10^{-2} M, $[\text{NaOH}] = 0.3$ M, $\mu = 1.0$ M at 25°

0.7×10^{-1} to 10.0×10^{-1} M for sorbitol.

Mechanism : Taking the above observations in view at lower concentrations of reactants, the following rate expression may be suggested,

$$-\frac{d[\text{Fey}]}{dt} = k[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}][\text{OH}][\text{S}] \quad (1)$$

where k is the rate constant. The observed k values were found to be 0.98×10^{-2} , 2.00×10^{-2} and 1.75×10^{-2} $\text{mol}^{-2} \text{dm}^{-6} \text{s}^{-1}$ for ethyl glycol, D-mannitol and D-sorbitol respectively.

Fig. 2 Effect of [Substrate] on the reaction rate (A) mannitol $[K_3Fe(CN)_6] = 2.5 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[NaOH] = 0.5 M$, $\mu = 0.915 M$ at 30° , (B) sorbitol $[K_3Fe(CN)_6] = 3.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[NaOH] = 0.5 M$, $\mu = 0.8 M$ at 30° and (C) [ethyl glycol] $[K_3Fe(CN)_6] = 3.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[NaOH] = 0.5 M$, $\mu = 1.0 M$ at 25°

The literature reveals that the oxidation of organic substrates takes place both with $Fe(CN)_6^{3-}$ ion and $KFe(CN)_6^{2-}$ ion. This is because when $Fe(CN)_6^{3-}$ ion is used as oxidant in aqueous alkaline medium in presence of potassium chloride, the following equilibrium exists,

It is also reported that the equilibrium³ also lies mainly towards right.

Thus, in order to explain the aforesaid results the reaction mechanism considering $Fe(CN)_6^{3-}$ and $KFe(CN)_6^{2-}$ ions as oxidants is proposed in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

In Scheme 1, (C₁) and (C₂) represent the labile complex between substrate anion and $KFe(CN)_6^{2-}$ ion as well as substrate anion and $Fe(CN)_6^{3-}$ ion respectively. The complexes formed in steps (III) and (IV) disproportionate at a faster rate as represented in steps (V) and (VI), but the oxidation rate would also depend on the concentration of the species of hexacyanoferrate(III) ion. Now from the steps (III) and (IV) the rate of disappearance of hexacyanoferrate(III) ion would be given by equation (2),

$$-\frac{d[Fe]}{dt} = k_2[S^-][KFe(CN)_6^{2-}] + k_3[S^-][Fe(CN)_6^{3-}] \quad (2)$$

In order to derive the final rate law equation it would be most appropriate to assume the total hexacyanoferrate(III) ion concentration as

$$[Fe(CN)_6^{3-}]_T = [Fe(CN)_6^{3-}] + [KFe(CN)_6^{2-}] \quad (3)$$

Thus, considering the steady state condition and equation (3), the final rate law equation in terms of decreasing

Fig. 3 Effect of $[OH^-]$ on the reaction rate (A) [mannitol] = $1.0 \times 10^{-1} M$, $[K_3Fe(CN)_6] = 5.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, $\mu = 1.05 M$ at 30° , (B) [sorbitol] = $3.0 \times 10^{-2} M$, $[K_3Fe(CN)_6] = 3.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, $\mu = 1.02 M$ at 30° and (C) [ethyl glycol] = $3.0 \times 10^{-2} M$, $[K_3Fe(CN)_6] = 3.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, $\mu = 1.0 M$ at 25°

hexacyanoferrate(III) ion concentration would be given by equation (4),

$$-\frac{d[\text{Fey}]}{dt} = \frac{2k_1[\text{S}][\text{OH}^-][\text{Fey}]_T\{k_3 + k_2(\text{KK}^+)\}}{k_{-1}[1 + (\text{KK}^+)] + [\text{Fey}]_T\{k_3 + k_2(\text{KK}^+)\}} \quad (4)$$

The derived rate law equation (4) is almost consistent with the observed kinetics, i.e. it shows first order kinetics with respect to substrate and hydroxide ion concentrations as well as the retarding trend with respect to hexacyanoferrate(III) ion concentration.

At higher concentrations of hexacyanoferrate(III), the values of $[\text{Fey}]_T\{k_3 + k_2(\text{KK}^+)\}$ will be large as compared to $k_{-1}(1 + \text{KK}^+)$ and hence in order to verify the results equation (4) can be rewritten as equation (5),

$$\frac{1}{R} = \frac{k_{-1}[1 + (\text{KK}^+)]}{2k_1[\text{S}][\text{OH}^-][\text{Fey}]_T\{k_3 + k_2(\text{KK}^+)\}} + \frac{1}{2k_1[\text{S}][\text{OH}^-]} \quad (5)$$

where, $R = -\frac{d[\text{Fey}]}{dt}$

The linear plot of $1/R$ vs $1/[\text{Fey}]_T$ confirms the validity of the rate law equation (5) and the proposed reaction mechanism. The values of k_1 , calculated from the intercept of the plot, are as follows: 4.76×10^{-5} for ethyl glycol, 1.00×10^{-3} for D-mannitol, and $2.20 \times 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$ for D-sorbitol. The final oxidation products of ethyl glycol, D-mannitol and D-sorbitol are ethylglycollic acid, D-mannaric acid and D-glucaric acid respectively.

Experimental

The standard solution of hexacyanoferrate(III) ion was prepared from A.R. (B.D.H.) sample. D-Mannitol, D-sorbitol and ethyl glycol (A.R., B.D.H.) used. Stock solution of NaOH (A.R., B.D.H.) was prepared in double-distilled water. The ionic strength of the medium was kept constant by using KCl (G.R., E. Merck). The progress of the reaction was followed by estimating the amount of hexacyanoferrate(II) ion produced after a definite time-interval with a solution of ceric(IV) sulphate using ferroin as a redox indicator. The products were identified by tlc⁴.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (A.G.) is thankful to U.G.C., New Delhi, for financial assistance and Research Associateship.

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